

Resolution of Co-ordinated Inorganic Compounds into Optical Isomers. Part I. Resolution of Triethylenediamino-cadmium Chloride, Bromide, Iodide and Sulphate.

BY PANCHANAN NEOGI AND GOPAL KRISHNA MUKHERJEE.

Existing literature shows that though several complex ethylenediamine compounds of trivalent metals like Cr, Co, etc., have been successfully resolved into their optical isomers, all attempts at resolution of ethylenediamine complexes of divalent metals like Ni, Zn, Cd, etc., have all along met with failure, among which may be mentioned the attempts of Bucknall and Wardlaw (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2739) who tried to resolve triethylenediamino-nickel chloride by means of *d*-camphor sulphonic acid, *d*-tartaric acid, etc. Tris-dipyridyl compounds of divalent metals have, however, been resolved into optical isomers. Werner (*Ber.*, 1912, 45, 433) was able to resolve tris-dipyridyl-ferrous salts and recently Morgan and Burstall (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2213) have successfully resolved tris- α -pipyridyl-nickel chloride into their optical isomers by means of *d*- and *l*-ammonium tartrates.

In this paper attempts have been made to resolve triethylenediamino-cadmium salts into optical isomers by means of *d*-tartaric acid, *d*-camphor sulphonic acid, *d*-bromocamphor sulphonic acid, and *d*-sodiocamphor nitronate, when success was achieved with the last reagent only. *d*-Sodiocamphor nitronate was used by Werner himself in the resolution of triethylenediamino complexes of trivalent metals like chromium (*Ber.*, 1912, 45, 865) in cases where other reagents failed to resolve. It appears, however, that this reagent has not hitherto been used for the resolution of the complex salts of divalent metals.

The *d*-tartrate, *d*-camphor sulphonate, and *d*-bromocamphor sulphonate of the cadmium complex were prepared and fractionally crystallised, but in all these cases the different fractions were found to have the same specific rotation and on removing the active residues, the resulting cadmium salt was found to be inactive. *d*-Sodiocamphor nitronate was then made use of in a way similar to that of

Werner in the case of complex chromium compounds (*loc. cit.*); but in this case no precipitate of the active substance occurred even when concentrated solutions of both the substances were taken. So the solution containing triethylenediamino-cadmium chloride and *d*-sodiocamphor nitronate was slowly evaporated in vacuum, when *d*-triethylenediamino-cadmium camphor nitronate slowly crystallised out. Three crops of crystals were thus collected which differed widely in their rotatory powers. On removing the camphor nitronate residue from the first fraction by means of dilute hydrochloric acid, the solution of the chloride was found to remain *dextro*-rotatory. It however, very soon racemised and crystallisation in vacuum yielded a *racemic* compound. But if to a fairly concentrated solution of the active salt excess of acetone be added, a crystalline precipitate of the active cadmium salt was obtained. The active solid retained its activity longer than its solution. The composition of the active substance was the same as that of the *racemic* salt.

The *laevo* variety of the substance could not, however, be obtained from the later fractions.

Attempts were then made to obtain the *laevo* variety by means of nitrocamphor itself, which is a *laevo*-rotatory substance, but up till now all attempts in this direction have met with failure. Further work is being done to isolate the *laevo* variety.

These salts which possess water of crystallisation lost weight when subjected to desiccation over concentrated sulphuric acid in vacuum and this fact was taken advantage of in the determination of the water of crystallisation.

The cadmium was estimated as cadmium sulphate in a platinum basin.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of d-triethylenediamino-cadmium tartrate.—Triethylenediamino-cadmium chloride was prepared according to the method used by Werner and co-workers (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1899, 21, 201). A concentrated solution of triethylenediamino-cadmium chloride (4 g.) was triturated with silver tartrate (4 g.) (prepared from a concentrated solution of Rochelle salt by precipitation with concentrated silver nitrate solution, washing with water and drying in a desiccator covered with black paper). The residue of silver chloride was repeatedly extracted with hot water and the extract filtered and evaporated in vacuum. Various fractions of crystals were thus obtained and all on

further purification by crystallisation gave a constant nitrogen content. (Found: N, 17.2; Cd, 22.4; H₂O, 10.8; [Cd (En)₃] (C₄H₄O₆), 3 H₂O requires N, 17.0; Cd, 22.73; H₂O, 10.93 per cent).

Rotation of this substance was measured in a 2 dcm. tube; after four crystallisations the values of $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ for the the first and the last fractions were 18.75° and 18.70° respectively. The tartrate was converted to the corresponding chloride by means of barium chloride but in each case the resulting solution was inactive.

Preparation of d-triethylenediamino-cadmium camphor sulphonate.—Freshly prepared silver oxide, obtained from AgNO₃ solution by precipitation with caustic soda and washing the residue with distilled water till free from the alkali salts, was dissolved in a warm solution of *d*-camphor sulphonic acid in water till a solution, neutral to litmus, was obtained. To a solution of triethylenediamino-cadmium chloride (5 g.) in water, the solution of the silver salt thus prepared was added till on adding one drop more it caused no further precipitate. The solution was filtered, evaporated in vacuum and fractionally crystallised and the different fractions further purified by recrystallisation. None of these fractions contained any chlorine and each gave a constant nitrogen content. (Found: N, 11.1; Cd, 14.27; H₂O, 2.3. [Cd(En)₃] (C₁₀H₁₅O₄S)₂, H₂O requires N, 10.88; Cd, 14.55; H₂O, 2.33 per cent).

Rotations of the different fractions were observed in a 2 dcm. tube. After four crystallisations the values of $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ for all these fractions were +15.0°. On acidifying a concentrated solution of any of these fractions with dilute hydrochloric acid and adding excess of acetone, triethylenediamino-cadmium chloride was precipitated which was found to be quite inactive.

Preparation of d-triethylenediamino-cadmium bromocamphor sulphonate.—A solution of the silver salt of *d*-bromocamphor sulphonic acid was prepared in the same way as the silver salt of *d*-camphor sulphonic acid by dissolving silver oxide in a warm solution of *d*-bromocamphor sulphonic acid till a solution neutral to litmus was obtained. To a solution of triethylenediamino-cadmium chloride (5 g.) in water, the silver bromocamphor sulphonate solution thus prepared was added till the addition of one drop more caused no further precipitate. The solution was filtered and the residue of silver chloride washed with water and the filtrate evaporated and fractionally crystallised and the different fractions purified by further crystallisation. None of these fractions was found to

to contain any chlorine and each gave the same nitrogen content. (Found: N, 8.5; Cd, 11.03; H₂O, 9.15. [Cd(En)₃] (C₁₀H₁₄BrSO₄)₂, 5H₂O requires N, 8.38; Cd, 11.21; H₂O, 8.98 per cent).

Rotations of the different fractions were observed in a 2 dcm. tube. Each of the four fractions showed the value of $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ to be +138.0°. On acidifying a concentrated solution of any of these fractions in water with hydrochloric acid and adding acetone in excess, the complex cadmium chloride was precipitated which was found to be quite inactive.

Preparation of d-triethylenediamino-cadmium camphor nitronate.—To a solution of triethylenediamino-cadmium chloride (4 g.) in water (10 c.c.) was added *d*-sodiocamphor nitronate (4.5 g.) dissolved in 15 c.c. of water and the mixture well shaken. No precipitate appeared. The solution was then subjected to fractional crystallisation in vacuum. The first fraction was recrystallised from water as very light yellow needles. This was completely free from chlorine. (Found: N, 15.7; Cd, 15.3; H₂O, 4.89. [Cd(En)₃] (C₁₀H₁₄O₃N)₂, 2H₂O requires N, 15.55; Cd, 15.6; H₂O, 5.0 per cent).

Rotation of this substance was observed in a 2 dcm. tube with a 5% solution and the value of the $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ was found to be +133.2°. The second and the third fractions on further purification by crystallisation were found to have identical chemical composition and their specific rotations were +97.4° and +94.7° respectively under identical conditions.

d-Triethylenediamino-cadmium chloride.—*d*-Triethylenediamino-cadmium camphor nitronate (first fraction) (2 g.) was dissolved in the least quantity of water and to the clear yellowish solution moderately dilute hydrochloric acid was added drop by drop and shaken till all the nitrocamphor had precipitated out and the solution became colourless which was then filtered and the residue washed with a small quantity of water. To the filtrate excess of acetone was added whereby a perfectly white crystalline substance was precipitated which was allowed to settle. The supernatant liquid was then decanted off and the precipitate washed several times with acetone to remove all traces of the acid and any free nitrocamphor. The residue was quickly dried underneath a fan between filter papers. (Found: N, 23.24; Cl, 19.45; Cd, 30.85. [Cd(En)₃]Cl₂ requires N, 23.15; Cl, 19.29; Cd, 30.79 per cent).

The substance (0.06 g.) was then dissolved in 15 c.c. of water and examined in a 2 dcm. tube when rotation was found to be +91°.

which makes $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, $+113.7^\circ$ and $[M]$, $+413.80^\circ$. The activity of the solution on being kept diminished rapidly and almost vanished in about an hour and a half. Examined after half an hour the specific rotation of the substance was found to be $+51.28^\circ$ under identical conditions. The solid, however, was found to be more stable when kept cool and examined after 3 hours, its specific rotation was found to be $+12.5^\circ$ under identical conditions, but when kept at the ordinary temperature (30°) it was found to be quite inactive after 2 hours.

d-Triethylenediamino-cadmium bromide was prepared in the same way as the chloride by decomposing the *d*-triethylenediamino-cadmium camphor nitronate (first fraction) with dilute hydrobromic acid and precipitation with acetone. (Found: N, 18.76; Br, 35.6; Cd, 24.49. $[\text{Cd}(\text{En})_3] \text{Br}_2$ requires N, 18.59; Br, 35.42; Cd, 24.72 per cent).

Rotation of the substance (0.05 g. in 15 c.c. water) was determined in a 2 dcm. tube and was found to be $+0.70^\circ$ which makes the $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, $+105.0^\circ$ and $[M]$, $+474^\circ$. The solution completely racemised in 1 hour where as the solid, if kept cool was found to have a specific rotation of $+7.5^\circ$ after 3 hours, under identical conditions.

d-Triethylenediamino-cadmium iodide was prepared in the same way as the chloride by decomposing the *d*-triethylenediamino-cadmium camphor nitronate (first fraction) with hydroiodic acid, and precipitation with acetone. (Found: N, 15.56; I, 46.86; Cd, 20.26. $[\text{Cd}(\text{En})_3] \text{I}_2$ requires N, 15.41; I, 46.43; Cd, 20.53 per cent).

Rotation of the substance was measured in a 2 dcm. tube with a solution of it (0.06 g.) in water (15 c.c.) and was found to be $+0.72^\circ$ which makes $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, $+90^\circ$ and $[M]$, 491.4° . The iodide solution also racemised as readily as the bromide. The solid when kept cool and examined after 2 hours was found to be quite inactive.

d-Triethylenediamino-cadmium sulphate was also prepared in just the same way as the other salts by decomposing the *d*-triethylenediamino-cadmium camphor nitronate (first fraction) with dilute sulphuric acid and precipitation with acetone. (Found: N, 21.95; Cd, 29.12; SO_4 , 24.30. $[\text{Cd}(\text{En})_3] \text{SO}_4$ requires N, 21.65; Cd, 28.94; SO_4 , 24.72 per cent).

Rotation of the substance was determined in a 2 dcm. tube with a solution of it (0.12 g.) in water (15 c.c.) and was found

to be 1.33° which makes $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, $+83.1^\circ$ and $+ [M]$, 322° . The sulphate solution was found to be stabler than those described above as it retained its activity almost undiminished for half an hour but it also was found to be inactive when examined after 3 hours. The solid (kept cool) when examined after 3 hours was found to have a specific rotation of $+6.25^\circ$ under identical conditions.

The corresponding active zinc salts were at first obtained in solution and have now been obtained in the solid condition. Further work on other salts is in progress.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE,
CALCUTTA.

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